

Maintainers and restorers identified in some rice cultivars of Pakistan

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We crossed 38 aromatic and nonaromatic local rice varieties and lines with IR58025 A and IR62829 A wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines from IRRI during 1994 kharif season. Seventy-six F₁ hybrids, their male parents, and two isogenic maintainers were transplanted in rows of 30 plants with 23-cm spacing on each side. The crop received 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60 kg P ha⁻¹. Standard agronomic and plant protection measures were used.

Ten plants from each hybrid were labeled. Three panicles from each of these plants were marked and bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as a percentage of filled grains. Five spikelets from the upper part of each panicle were collected before anthesis and fixed in 70% alcohol. Two to three anthers from each spikelet were placed onto a glass slide, squashed in 1% IKI solution, and screened for sterile and fertile pollens. Fertile pollens, which became deeply stained, were round and fully developed.

Male parents of the hybrids with 100% pollen and spikelet sterility were classified as potential maintainers, those with 80-100% pollen and spikelet fertility as restorers, and the rest as partial restorers.

Frequency of maintainers (63%) was much higher than that of restorers among 76 hybrids tested (see table). 1021-8 and KS282 were the only potential restorers for both CMS lines, whereas Basmati 385 restored fertility only in IR58025 A (>80%), indicating that marked cytoplasmic nuclear interaction exists and expression of restorer genes varies with the genetic background of

Maintainer and restorer lines identified for IRRI CMS lines at Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan. 1994-95.

Pollen parent	Spikelet fertility of hybrids with ^a	
	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
KS282	R	R
IR6	B	B
49744	PR	PR
4048-3	B	B
Basmati 385	R	PR
4029-A	PR	PR
4029-B	B	B
4439	PR	PR
50189-8-6	PR	PR
40555	PR	PR
GP-6	B	B
GP-10	PR	PR
GP-15	B	B
GP-16	B	B
GP-43	B	B
4029-2	B	B
4029-3	PR	PR
Basmati 5854	PR	PR
47456	B	B
PK3732-28	B	B
C622	PR	PR
Jhona 349	PR	PR
PK3717-12	B	B
PK3727-2	B	B
DR82	B	B
Basmati 370	B	B
1021-8	R	R
4289	B	B
4334	B	B
4365	B	B
PK3355-5-1-4	B	B
PK3303-7-2	B	B
49818	B	B
33608	B	B
50020	B	B
50021	B	B
Basmati 198	B	B
Basmati 6129	PR	PR

^aR = restorer (80-100% pollen and spikelet fertility).
PR = partial restorer (5-79% pollen and spikelet fertility).
B = maintainer (100% pollen and spikelet sterility).

female parents. Apparently, restorers among Pakistani rice cultivars are scarce.

Maintainer lines identified are being used in a backcrossing program for inducing CMS in local germplasm. Restorer lines 1021-8, KS282, and Basmati 385 will be used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■

Development of rice cytoplasmic male sterile line 47456 A in Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan

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Hybrid rice research was initiated at Kala Shah Kaku in 1991. We crossed IRRI cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A, with wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm, with aromatic rice breeding line 47456 in 1992. 47456 [4048-3/PK4112 (Basmati 370/4439)] has extra-long grains and short stature, and flowers early. Plants in the F₁ were raised in 1993. Crosses of IR58025 A and IR62829 A with 47456 showed complete pollen sterility as well as spikelet sterility under bagged conditions (see table).

Backcrosses were made with recurrent parent 47456. The derived progenies (F₁, BC₁, and BC₂) and the parents were transplanted in the field in rows of 30 plants at 23-cm spacing from each side in Jul 1995. The crop received 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60 kg P ha⁻¹. Standard agronomic and plant protection measures were followed.

Ten plants from each generation were selected, with three panicles from each plant bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as the percentage of filled grains. Five spikelets from the upper part of each panicle were collected before anthesis and fixed in 70% alcohol. Two to three anthers from each spikelet were squashed in 1% IKI solution to determine pollen sterility. Complete pollen sterility was observed in the F₁ and backcross generations, indicating successful transfer of CMS from IR58025 A and IR62829 A into Basmati line 47456. Restorers for the Basmati CMS line 47456 A are being identified. ■